

English Proficiency of Grade 9 Junior High Students

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ABSTRACT

The resurgence of English proficiency has fallen to an abysmally low level on the ability of learners to fluently speak, read and write due to the effects on the language environment and preference as exposed in mass/social media, technology-based and printed reading materials. Thus, this study was aimed to determine the level of English Proficiency of Grade 9 Junior High Students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School. This descriptive-evaluative research design was employed using survey instruments which used to measure the level of proficiency in English. Findings revealed that television is the most available in their environment while the language preference of these respondents was English-Filipino. The overall level of English proficiency across eight language areas is developing. Results further revealed that there is a significant relationship between the students' language preference and English language proficiency. Hence, Computer Aided Instructional Materials are recommended to integrate on their lessons so that low-performing students become proficient in English.

Keywords: *English Proficiency, Language Environment, Language Preference, Grammar, Structure, Idioms, Vocabulary, Verbal Analogy*

INTRODUCTION

1. THE PROBLEM AND ITS SETTING

A person who is proficient in English may have unlimited access to the world's known scientific and technological discoveries that are predominantly written in English. This means that for a better grasp of knowledge in English, students should be more exposed in Mass Media, Technology, and Printed Reading Materials (Alngog, 2013). In connection with the relationship between language environment and language preference to the English language proficiency, it is presumed that students who have

high proficiency in English are expected to perform well in English as a subject and in other school subjects. Thus, this study investigates on the English Proficiency of Grade Nine Junior High Students at which grade level the researcher is assigned.

Department of Education Officials (DO No. 72, s. 2011), agreed that proficiency in the English language depends on the nature of the environment and the language preference that these learners are exposed and developed their skills. More advanced communication skills and adept in technology-based materials on the internet such as Facebook, Instagram, Skype, Edmodo, Quipper, Twitter, Emails, Google Chrome, etc. can attain success in academic pursuits.

The study conducted in Jose Sanvictores Sr. High School in Cagwait District, Division of Surigao del Sur. Grade 9 students served as the respondents because these are the kind of learners who are more technologically inclined and adventurous but with the lowest results in their Mean Percentage Score during the first and second quarters of SY 2016-2017.

As Aina and Ogundele (2013) claimed, language proficiency in English is significantly related to academic performance. Academic subjects like Science, Mathematics, and English often requires the use of language functions. The language plays a significant role in critical and analytical thinking required in any subjects. The more functions with which students are adept, the more effective their thinking can be. Thus, the more the students are proficient in the English language, the more they are likely to perform well in their academic subjects.

In the K to 12 Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum, DepEd puts emphasis on the competencies on learning the English language effectively to have a

pool of manpower that is globally competitive. It implies that proficiency in the English language is necessary skill and knowledge as well as a necessary attribute to meet the challenges of the 21st century (Alngog, 2013). However, various studies reveal that in the Philippines the quality of education is continuously declining. This notion based on the results of achievement tests where the academic performance of the students attributed to their proficiency in the English language. In Caraga Administrative Region, the English language proficiency of the secondary students has deteriorated in several ways: incorrect grammar, lack of fluency, poor reading comprehension, lack of interest in reading, and disorganized writing (Bagnol, 2014). As a matter of fact, the NAT Mean Percentage Score Reports of School Year 2014 in Surigao del Sur Division that 56.20% in English as a quantifier of the division's performance remained in the bottom ranking. This lack of language skills manifested in several ways – weak in structure, the inability to use English in connected discourse, poor reading comprehension skills and the lack of interest in reading. NETRC (2014) claimed that the declining results was due to the effects of language environment and preference in Mass Media, Technology, and Printed Reading Materials that these learners were more exposed.

Given the established gaps, the student's level of language performance in these skills was empirically investigated if the levels of English proficiency has a significant relationship to the language environment and language preference among Grade 9 Junior High School Students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School. The results of the study then basically helped the school heads, teachers, and students in improving the English Proficiency among the students in intensifying its implementation scheme.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This study anchored on Cognitive Academic Language Proficiency which delineates the connection between students' cognitive and linguistic processes to their academic performance. There are two levels of language proficiency. These are the basic interpersonal communicative skills and the cognitive academic language proficiency. The basic interpersonal communicative skills concept signifies the students' language informal conversation. These are used by students when they talk about their parents, siblings, and peers in real settings and

situations, that is; situations in which the context offers cues that make an understanding not dependent on verbal interaction alone (Racca and Lasaten, 2016). Cummins (2013) refers to this conversational ability as context embedded or contextualized where the conversation is natural and deals with ordinary matters requiring speakers to react and respond to each other.

Meanwhile, according to Cummins (2013), cognitive academic language proficiency is the type of language needed in the educational settings. Classroom activities like reading, writing, participating in formal conversations and taking exams are some of the tasks that require cognitive academic language proficiency. Thus, students who have not yet developed their cognitive academic language proficiency may encounter difficulties in learning science, mathematics and other academic subjects.

The theory on cognitive academic language proficiency, therefore, provided a reason to study and investigate the relationship between English language proficiency and the language environment and language preference of Grade 9 Junior High Students. Based on Figure 1, it conceptualized that the English language proficiency of the Grade 9 students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. High School affects their English language. This study believes that if the students have high English language proficiency, they are more likely to perform well in their academics, particularly in the said subject.

On the other hand, the theoretical framework of this study is also derived from the multiple intelligence theory discovered by a psychologist, Howard Gardner (1983) as revised in 2011 in his book, *Frames of Mind*. The theory suggests that "there are at least seven ways that people have of perceiving and understanding the world." Gardner labels "each of these ways a distinct 'intelligence' -- in other words, a set of skills allowing individuals to find and resolve genuine problems they face" (discover-multiple-intelligences.com, 2012).

One of these ways of Intelligence is Linguistic Intelligence that "involves sensitivity to spoken and written language, the ability to learn languages, and the capacity to use language to accomplish certain goals. This intelligence includes the ability to effectively use language on oneself rhetorically or poetically; and language as a means to remember

information. The reason for adopting this theory is that it is related to the variable in the study.

Limited English proficient student defined as a student whose first language is a language other than English who is unable to perform classroom works in English (Driscoll, 2013). The definition of English language proficiency adopted in this study is the ability to demonstrate the classroom works in English since this definition associates to the other variable in the study (language environment and language preference). In this study, English language proficiency was investigated through the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of Grade 9 Junior High Students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School.

To apply this theory in this study, individuals must master the rules, the meaning of words and how these words derive meaning and express their thoughts. Thus, these theories intertwined with academic success which functions several variables in the language of instruction. Hence, the conceptual framework gives an overview on how things viewed as a significant tool in making an appropriate solution to the problems. The schematic diagram that follows showed the salient steps taken to address the issue on English language proficiency among students and teachers. The use of the result of the standardized test in English proficiency and the survey questionnaires would bring concerned people to an awareness of the real scenario in the classroom as regards to the ability of students to become proficient in English.

Figure1. Schematic Diagram of the Study

On the first box, the respondents delved with consideration on the following indicators: Language Environment like (1) mass media which include television, radio, and musical gadget; (2) Technology-Based Materials comprising the internet, cellular phones, and DVD/movies; (3) Printed Reading

Materials such as books, newspapers/magazines, dictionaries/thesaurus, and pocketbooks/novels. The respondents also asked about the language preference: English, Filipino, Filipino-English, Tandaganon, and another language which they preferred to use at home, in school, and in the community.

A second box is then drawn to connect the dependent variables which are the actual results of the English Proficiency test in the eight language areas: grammar, structure, idiomatic expressions, vocabulary, verbal analogy, logical organization of ideas, identification of errors, and reading comprehension. By these, levels of proficiency of the students under each area revealed. This second box determined the type of intervention program among grade 9 junior high school students. In this study, English Proficiency pertains to the DepEd Order No. 72, s. 2011 in identifying the eight learning areas for English Proficiency: grammar, structure, idioms, vocabulary, and verbal analogy, logical organization of ideas, identification of errors and reading comprehension. The third box is the output of the study which is a proposed intervention program to improve English Language proficiency of the students.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to analyze the English proficiency of Grade 9 students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School, Cagwait, Surigao del Sur which became the basis for the intervention proposed in the study. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What language environment do Grade 9 students are exposed to:
 - 1.1 Mass media;
 - 1.2 Technology-based materials;
 - 1.3 Printed reading materials?
2. What is the preferred language of the respondents from the identified language environment?
3. What is the proficiency level of the Grade 9 students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School in the eight language areas on the following indicators:
 - 3.1 Grammar;
 - 3.2 Structure;
 - 3.3 Idioms;
 - 3.4 Vocabulary;
 - 3.5 Analogy
 - 3.6 Logical organization;
 - 3.7 Identifying errors;
 - 3.8 Reading comprehension?
4. Is there a significant relationship between language environment and the language preference?

5. What intervention plan can be institutionalized to enhance the English Proficiency levels of Grade 9 students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School?

Null Hypothesis

Problems number 1, 2 and 3 are hypotheses free. Problem number 4 hypothesize as:

HO1: There is no significant relationship between the language environment and the language preference of the student-respondents.

Significance of the Study: This study is expected to provide significant contributions to the academic community and the country in general. This study is deemed beneficial to the following entities:

English Teachers: This study would develop their awareness on the need to use teaching approaches and methods that require reflective and creative thinking as well as active participation of the learners.

School Administration: This study could be of great help to the administrators encouraging them to conduct service-training or send their teachers to attend seminars as workshops in methods of teaching English Proficiency in Secondary level.

High School Students: This study would help them to strengthen their coverage and enthusiasm to perform English activities using the interactive, cooperative and collaborative designs together with their peers. Therefore, it develops their creative and analytical thinking in gathering and interpreting data and draw findings, conclusions, and recommendations anchored with different theories.

Teachers in Other Academic Subjects: This study could provide a database that can use as a reference for more meaningful educational services. Results could be useful in the solution of problems related to English language teaching and learning.

Researchers: This study serves as a guide for them to develop instructional materials contributory for the enhancement of instructional functions.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study conducted in Jose Sanvictores Sr. High School in Cagwait District, Division of Surigao del Sur. Among 420 students enrolled this current school year, only grade 9 students were administered the test using purposive sampling method. These respondents

were the focus of the study because these are the students who are more technologically inclined and adventurous but with the lowest results in their Mean Percentage Score during first and second quarters.

It limits on the analysis of Grade 9 students in English Proficiency-based on the following parts: (a) grammar; (b) structure; (c) idioms; (d) vocabulary; (e) analogy; (f) organization of ideas; (g) error identification and (h) reading comprehension. The instrument was tested by students enrolled in Grade 9 of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School, Cagwait, Surigao del Sur, of the Academic Year 2016-2017. They are considered to be the respondents because of the direct contact with the researcher assigned to such grade level.

A standardized test questionnaires from the Curriculum and Implementation Division (CID) in the Division of Surigao del Sur utilized in this study. The scope of these tools is anchored on DepEd Order No. 91, s. 2009 specifying the Policy Guidelines and Requirements Regulating the National Test Instruments and its Results.

Definition of Terms: To facilitate clear understanding, the following terms operationally defined in this study:

English Proficiency: It refers to the language environment and the language preference where the student-respondents of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School in Cagwait, Surigao del Sur are exposed to the ability to perform the functions of communication at levels of proficiency necessary to function in society.

Grammar: Refers to the class of words, its relation and use in the sentence. It is also the manner of making the subject-predicates agree in person and number.

Identification of Errors: It is the ability to identify sentence errors such as the subject and verb agreement and the tenses of the verb when making revisions.

Idiomatic Expressions: These are the type of English that have a meaning different from the meaning of the words in the expression.

Language Environment: It refers to educational approach, cultural context, or physical setting in

which teaching and learning occur. It is also a factor as a characteristics of the teachers, instructional group, or institution, the learning styles and pedagogies used and the societal culture of where the learning is occurring.

Language Preference: It refers to the preferred human speech used in every day communication. The language most preferred by native and non-English speakers prevalent among Filipino students are English, Filipino and English, Filipino and the vernacular or the native language.

Logical Organization of Ideas: It refers to the logical order of sentences in a paragraph. It is to arrange sentences in order of importance which can be done by either moving from the most important point to the least important on going the opposite way.

Mass Media: It refers to technology that is intended to reach a mass audience. It is the primary means of communication used to reach the vast majority of the general public. The common platforms of mass media are newspapers, magazines, radio, television, and the internet where students can gather various sources of information.

Printed Reading Materials: It refers to the printed materials used by the teachers to facilitate teaching-learning among the grade 9 students which designed to capacitate students for better comprehension.

Reading Comprehension: This term means an understanding of what the learner understands what he or she reads. It is an act of grasping an idea or process with the intellect.

Technology - Based Materials: It refers to the electronic materials extracted from the internet or any technology-based instrument as used by the teachers to effectively enhance the proficiency levels of the students designed to capacitate students for better understanding of the text.

Structure: It refers to the manner in which words are arranged and related on a given text or sentence.

Verbal Analogy: It refers to one pair of related words to another without its pair. The student must find a word or words that have the same relationship to the word as the first pair.

Vocabulary: It is all about words in a language or a set of words that the students are trying to learn

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter features existing educational research literature and studies that involve analysis of English Proficiency of Junior High School students. The research has been synthesized, organized and highlights the background information.

Related Literature

Foreign

Language teaching involves difficult decisions regarding when teaching should start, what the curriculum should include and which methods should be used (Güngör & Öğretir, 2008). To answer these questions, the factors that affect language learning should be known first. Hashemi (2011) identified that students' weakness in English language learning is due to the differences in social contexts, cultural environments. Differences in mediating effect of intensity of language education are one factor that identified by researchers specifically on different teaching intensity of English classes in a particular school.

English proficiency is that of learners' attitudes towards learning a foreign language. Research on this factor has conducted from different perspectives. Some looked at whether learners have positive or negative attitudes towards learning a foreign language (Abu-Rabia, 2003). Some other studies focused on the correlation between attitude and language proficiency level (Clément, 2013).

Poor language proficiency has been considered a barrier to learning and academic success at the higher education, where universities require students seeking admission to obtain a score on English language proficiency tests to indicate that they can achieve academically success (Williams, Powers, Kong & Starr, 2012).

English Language proficiency or linguistic proficiency referred to the ability of an individual to speak or perform in an acquired language. According to Blagojevich, Ruiz and Dunn(2004), English Language proficiency: English language learners' communication information, ideas, and concepts necessary for academic success in the content area of social studies.

Academic achievement is the outcome of an education-the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their educational goals. In this study, the definition of "the result of an education-the extent to which a student, teacher has achieved their educational goals" is adopted. In this study, academic achievement was investigated through the Grade Point Average (GPA) the student obtained from his/her postsecondary studies.

Everhard, Cooper, and Bock (2005) also stressed the importance of sentence in comprehension. Sentence sense is an additional component and therefore should taught. In this regard, the child must appreciate the unity of a sentence. He must familiarize to sense the relationship between parts.

The majority of the students who admitted into the University of Nigeria have no ample opportunity to study English Language, except those who are admitted to study English and related subjects such as linguistics and literature in English (Abebe & Davidson 2012). Though all students accepted into the universities in Nigeria are encouraged to take few courses in the use of English, the content of these English courses are grossly inadequate for the students to acquire requisite skills in effective use of language for communication and the give and take of social experience. To study English as a second language and be successful at it, the student must be helped by the teacher to acquire skills in the four language arts skills; namely: Speaking, reading, listening and writing.

A rich and stimulating language environment during the early years and beyond is essential to the development of verbal and intellectual skills necessary for language learning. Malinowski (2011), asserted that composition writing is a difficult skill to acquire, and recommended, therefore, that teachers must use a variety of methods for teaching the English Language. Ellis and Tomlison (2010), suggested some basic skills to be taught to learners so that they can write essays proficiently. Such skills include spelling, punctuation, and convention of style. Reyner et al., (2011), ascertained that "many good teachers are adaptive rather than rigid in their approach to teaching children and only loosely base their instruction on a given method." There are odds against the Nigerian students in learning English.

Reading habits According to Igbokwe (2012) are changing. Students are rarely interested in reading for pleasure and enjoyment instead they read only to pass on examination. Unfortunately, reading not taught as a separate subject in the curriculum. It is subsumed in every subject area and regarded as a tool facilitating other types of learning. According to Igbokwe (2012), student achievement has been declining in the recent years. Communication technology especially the internet is having an adverse effect on the learning culture. It discourages lazy students from engaging in serious reading. Most students spend more time in the cyber cafes, playing video games, browsing, and chatting with friends. The influence of these media is negative.

Language is the vehicle of social interaction, and there is a need for language to function properly, social interaction, and indeed, for functional literacy. It emphasized that "a person is functionally literate when he has acquired the knowledge and skills in reading and writing which enable him to engage effectively in all those activities in which literacy assumed in his culture of the group" (Gray, 2012). As pointed out by Richards (2011), in communicative language teaching classes, tasks and activities are designed to enable learners to achieve communicative objectives by participating in communicative processes such as exchanging information, negotiation of meaning, and interaction. In communicative language teaching, learner-centered learning emphasized.

Local

The importance of the English language proficiency is increasing day by day, for it is the universal language used in different transactions most especially in schools. With the advent of K-12 Curriculum, the government emphasizes the importance of learning the subject matter effectively through learning strategies. But in a classroom setting, those students who do not have good English background face many problems, since it is necessary to have a high English proficiency in understanding subjects that use English context such as mathematics, sciences, social science, humanities, etc.

The learning of language is in line with the training program on the implementation of the K to 12 Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum. This concept is also true in teaching English of the transition year, the ninth grade which is part of the Junior High

School. It seeks to develop citizenship and address communication needs, interpersonal informative and aesthetics of Filipino students for which is emerging as the Lingua Franca in line with developments in applied linguistics and pedagogy in consonance with the government thrust and globalization.

Evidently, students who graduate from high school face some problems with English when they start studying in colleges or universities. In some departments, such as Medicine, Law, and Engineering, there is a high intensity of English classes, and this has a strong effect on students' ability to pass their subjects. Students who do not have a good education in high school encounter more problems than the ones who have. The students of other departments are more likely to face these problems after graduation because it is often necessary to have a high proficiency in English to get a good job. The importance and necessity of English proficiency keep the eyes on the factors, and some background factors have researched (Gunes, 2011).

In the Philippines, a bilingual context where the role of English is made narrower with the expansion of the role of the Filipino national language, the theory of communicative competence considers the language as a tool for communication rather than the system of rules. Ability in the language is more of skill rather than a set of knowledge because English is a tool for instructional and academic purposes. Those in the field of teaching are expected to have the proficiency of English language as a means of access to scientific knowledge (Arpilleda 2013).

Related Studies

Foreign

Brown (2007) points out that, there is a depending and subordinating relationship between teaching and learning. It plays roles as guiding, facilitating learning, and setting the conditions for learning. Having a good understanding of how the learner learns will help teachers determine their philosophy of education, their style, approach, methods, and classroom techniques.

Cook (2011) believes the proof of teaching is in the learning and all successful teaching depends upon learning. Cook also states that there is no point in providing interesting, well-prepared language lessons if students do not learn from them. It's important for teachers and learners to understand the goal of

language teaching and learning, as well as how to achieve it. It is pointed out that the goal of language teaching is to develop learners' communicative competence (Liu, 2013). As advised in Rivers (2008), when selecting learning activities, one must always remember that the goal is for the students to be able to interact freely with others: to understand what others wish to communicate in the broadest sense and to be able to convey to others what they want to share.

Following this point, Liu (2013) believes that the ultimate goal of language instruction is to equip learners with the ability to use the language for their communication. This notion reasonably explains why the four macro language skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing) fall into the two categories: vocal and written communication. Listening and speaking considered the most important forms of vocal communication, whereas reading and writing belonged to the most important forms of written communication.

Aytar and Öğretir's (2008) study in Turkey of 350 parents whose children receive pre-school education shows that more than 80% of these parents accept that English should be taught in pre-school institutions. Similar results found by İltar and Er (2007) which support the view that parents and teachers think that English must taught in Turkey's preschool institutions.

Robertson (2013) emphasized that television or radio uses is primarily dependent on the audience with whom they are speaking to, speakers design their style primarily for and in response to their audience. In the case of mass media language, it is specifically patterned by the broadcaster with a particular audience in mind, and this determines what forms and content used; speakers respond primarily to their audience.

Although as policy changes, parents' and teachers' support reflect on the need for high-quality course delivery in English language teaching. Young learners comes with many problems among which the suitability of classroom activities and materials along with teachers' successful use is the leading one, Scott and Ytreberg (2010).

Özdemir and Uşun's (2009) found out that English language teachers considered themselves to be sufficient in using speaking, grammar, drama and

singing activities, but insufficient in using audio materials such as the tape recorder and CD player, using films and computers.

English language teachers' problems with tapes and CDs have reported in larger scale studies like that of Büyükduman's (2005) who suggested that tape recorders and cassettes should be distributed by the Ministry of National Education to Turkish primary schools' English language classes.

More research is needed to understand the nature of the activities employed in Turkish EFL classrooms. Teachers want their students to be competent in vocabulary and speaking. However, participants' answers to the first question show that students continue to be passive learners who learn through teacher-centered activities. It is problematic to see that these two realities cannot nurture each other to educate successful learners since students cannot be competent of a foreign language by learning vocabulary and speaking as passive learners. It is also problematic that teachers do not give importance to the culture of the language learned and taught.

The study results raised some interesting discussions about the role of learners in English classes. Through class observations, it found out that the students themselves are not passive. This finding confirms previous studies that found Vietnamese to be no longer passive (Mai & Iwashita, 2012). Instead of traditional whole-class settings, they prefer to participate in communicative activities that enable them to use the language to express themselves, explore problems and exchange ideas with their friends to acquire knowledge effectively (Mai & Iwashita, 2012).

Igbokwe (2012) observed that spending most of their time watching TV, the computer/internet, and cellular phones and not spending time in reading and writing would result in the decline of their scholastic achievement. He further mentioned that students are rarely interested in using the foreign language in interacting with peers. They are more interested in using their own language like Filipino in the Philippines. Moreover, Paropcar (2010) recommended that the students be guided of facilities such as libraries, as this could enhance their language development.

Although Vietnamese students are not completely passive, and although they prefer to participate in communicative activities, some de-motivating factors have prevented them from being active in English classes. The first reason is the students' lack of confidence in their English proficiency. Other factors, such as exam-oriented teaching and classes with students' English levels might also the application of learner-centered approaches and hinder the students' active participation in English classes. The learner-centered approach should be implemented to facilitate the active role of learners in English classes, (Mai & Iwashita, 2012).

Local

Alngog (2013) observes that secondary students show poor proficiency in the English language in expressing their feelings and in sharing their ideas. They find it hard to communicate various thoughts because of the lack of mastery of the English language. The majority is bereft of the lack of skills.

Tabula (2010) focuses on the linguistic errors of the speech communication. He looked into the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, course, type of high school graduated from, geographical location, parents' educational attainment, parents' work status, language used at home, exposure to mass media, and how these variables are related to the respondents' linguistic errors.

Baetiong and Cabayan (2010) serves to examine the use of language learning strategies by high school students when speaking in class and factors. Seventy junior students of the public school were observed and asked to answer 19-item language checklist result shows strategy to use to follow this order metacognitive social and comparative strategies subjects were classified among an adaptation of ACTEL proficiency guidelines. Results indicated a significant difference between groups in the level of frequency of which metacognitive strategies used and at which strategies orchestrated. These factors were used to influence strategy used.

The classroom teacher should follow as much as possible a systematic procedure, starting with the collection of data, conduct analysis and publish the results and findings. The teacher should seek feedback from colleagues at all stages of the process, process the final results in academic journals and refereed publications, sharing the results with others.

No matter if it is hard or easy to master a language, it is a prolonged and consistent period. Acquiring or learning a language requires much time and effort from not only the learners but from the teachers as well. Nowadays, when English considered as an international language, the activity of teaching and learning English as a foreign or second language is also examined and discussed widely all over the world (Alngog, 2013).

Synthesis

The literature and studies made as a basis on the formulation of the theoretical and conceptual framework of the study, the problem, hypotheses, and the summary by which the whole investigation was developed and conducted. As these studies above and views show, much research is needed to uncover all aspects of teaching English to young learners so that the quality of teaching increases as expected and planned.

The ideas of the authors compared to the language, the teaching of English students and teachers have inspired the researcher to focus on the use of various approaches on the English Proficiency of Grade 9 Junior High Students. Insights from the students cited had also helped in many ways. For example, educators faced with the challenge of addressing the needs of the growing number of students whose primary language is not English (Gibbons, 2003).

Insights from the studies cited had helped in many ways. For instance, the studies of Alngog, Baetiong, and Cabayan and Tabula strengthened the concepts of the relationship between language performance, and reading comprehension of the students and the connection between language environment and the students' oral communication ability significantly related to the investigation.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research methods which includes a brief description of the research respondents, environment, instruments used in the data gathering procedure, scoring and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study conducted through descriptive-evaluative method since its aim was to describe students' language environment and language preference and assess the English language proficiency levels.

Further, the study sought to determine their relationship between these variables to discover the extent to which they affected one another and how they caused the existing problem of English proficiency in junior high school.

The surveys made to ascertain the language environment among the respondents when they were on its real situation on the condition of practice. This method yielded quantitative information that analyzed statistically, and the selection of this design based on the objective of the study, the type of data and the analysis of data employed in the investigation. This technique acquired information through the distribution of questionnaires to the respondents, tabulating and summarizing the results of the responses.

Research Locale

The researcher conducted this study at Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School located at Barangay La Purisima, Cagwait, Surigao del Sur of Caraga (Region XIII). The school situated along the national roads in a hilly portion of the said barangay. It established in the year 2000 where there were six instructional buildings, and one non-instructional room constructed. Of the instructional rooms, all of them are standard rooms, meaning they meet the DepEd's guidelines for safety and usability. All in all, the school has at least one general academic classroom and office.

This school is a neophyte institution recognized as a Non-Implementing Unit (NIU) when it comes to financial management. It is an annex campus of Unidad National High School which offers Junior High School for Grades 7 to 10 and General Academic Strand (GAS) and Technical-Vocational Livelihood for the Grade 11 Senior High School Students. There are 16 teaching and non-teaching personnel of the school with 420 students enrolled in the current school year. Thus, figure 2 presents the geographical location of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School in the District of Cagwait, Division of Surigao del Sur.

Figure2. Geographical Location of JSSNS

Respondents of the Study

The researcher made use of purposive sampling technique because they were only two classes of Grade 9 Students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School. One class comprised of 47 students and other class had 49 students. Ninety-Six (96) students chosen as respondents of this study. Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents.

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents

	Total Population	Sample Respondents
Class A	47	47
Class B	49	49
Total	96	96

Research Instrument

Two questionnaires used to collect data for this study. The tools designed from the review of related literature and the conceptual framework to measure the independent and dependent variables. The first questionnaire was adopted from the study of Alngog (2013) which composed of survey questionnaire on the language environment and the language preference of the respondents. The instrument designed to draw the real situation among the respondents. Before the administering of the test, a written document considered. Thus, a letter of intent personally hand-delivered by the researcher to the author on Survey Questionnaire on Language

Environment and Language Preference (Alngog, 2013) to adopt his tool for the present study.

The second instrument used the standardized questionnaire from the Division of Surigao del Sur exploring the English proficiency of the respondents. The structured questionnaire had eight language areas: I. Grammar, II. Structure, III. Idiomatic Expressions, IV. Vocabulary, V. Verbal Analogy, VI. Logical Organization, VII. Identification of Errors, and VIII. Reading Comprehension.

The parameters used in this study based on DepEd Order No. 73, s. 2012 on the Guidelines in the Assessment and Levels of Proficiency under the K to 12 Curriculum in Public and Private Elementary and Secondary Schools Nationwide.

Weight Index of Performance	Level of Proficiency
5 89-100%	(A) Advanced
4 67-88%	(P) Proficient
3 45-66%	(AP) Approaching Proficiency
2 26-44%	(D) Developing
1 01-25%	(B) Beginning

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedures of this research followed in chronological order: First, a permit was required from the Faculty of the Graduate School of Surigao del Sur State University and a letter of intent to the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct this study. With the Superintendent's endorsement, the researcher gave the letter to School Principal of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School by administering the test to the student-respondents.

The study conducted on the usual teaching hours. The questionnaires administered to Grade 9 Junior High School students. The participants in this study informed that the data collected used in the conduct of research and not viewed by other students and teachers that not involved in this study. This done to secure the most honest and accurate responses from the students. Administration of the questionnaire to the students carried out for only 60 minute period in the first week of December 2016.

After administering the test, the questionnaires retrieved personally by the researcher to ensure its safe return with 100 percent retrieval. It then tallied, tabulated, analyzed, treated and interpreted with the

help of the statistician as to the levels of proficiency of the students in English.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools used to analyze the data of this study. To determine Problem number 1 on the language environment of the grade 9 students as to mass media, technology-based materials, and printed reading materials, frequency count employed. Problem number 2 on the language preference of student-respondents analyzed using Weighted Mean computation.

To determine the proficiency levels in the eight language areas the researcher employed the following: First, the Mean Percentage Score by using the formula to get the percentage. The result compared to the descriptive categories of the index of performance or index of proficiency of the eight language areas. Problem number 4 treated through Pearson Product Moment of Correlation (Pearson-r) to determine the significant relationships between the language preference and language areas. In the tests of hypotheses, the level of significance set at the .05 probability level.

4. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the data gathered from the two sets of instruments administered to Grade 9 students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School, the language environment and language preference survey and the English Proficiency test. The data gathered are herein presented, analyzed and interpreted based on the sequence of the statement of the problem.

Language Environment of the Grade 9 Junior High Students

Results on the language environment of Grade 9 Junior High Students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School as to the following indicators: mass media, technology-based materials, and printed reading materials presented in Table 2. Frequency counting and ranking were used to determine each category.

It can be gleaned from Table 2 that the study identified the groups of language environment. These were mass media available in their community such as television, radio and music gadgets. Technology-based materials like computer or the internet, cellular phones, DVD/movies some printed reading materials

such as books/textbooks, newspapers/magazines, dictionaries/thesaurus, pocketbooks/novels.

The Grade 9 student-respondents asked to check whether these materials found in their school, home or their community where they exposed.

Table 2 Language Environment of Grade 9 Students under Mass Media

Language Environment Mass Media	f	%	Rank
Television	64	67%	1
Radio	7	7%	3
Music Gadgets	25	26%	2
Total	96	100%	

Table 2 shows that about 64 of the students or 67% declared that they are exposed to television wherein this type of medium is available within ones to reach while 25 of the students or 26% preferred Music Gadgets and only seven students or 7% of them favored on Radio. This result supported by the study conducted by Alngog (2013) that 98% of students of Jacinto P. Elpa National High School preferred to watch televisions than other forms of mass media. They do not realize as observed by Igbokwe (2012) that most of their time spent on watching television would result in the decline of their academic performance, especially in English. It noted that reading books are better than watching TV as far as active learning is concerned, Shadi and Udopia (2012).

Table 3 Language Environment of Grade 9 Students under Technology - Based Materials

Language Environment Technology-Based Materials	f	%	Rank
Computer Internet (FB, Instagram, Twitter, Skype, Edmodo, Quip per, Twitter, Emails, Google Chrome, etc.)	42	44%	2
Cellphones	44	46%	1
DVD Movies	10	10%	3
Total	96	100%	

Technology-Based Materials on Table 3 reveals that 46% of the respondents more exposed to cellular phones and 44% of the respondents hooked in the computer/internet. The use of Cellphones is the easiest and most convenient way to communicate with their family, distant relatives, and friends; moreover, Computer/ Internet usage such as Facebook, Instagram, Skype, Edmodo, Quipper, Twitter, Emails,

Google Chrome and others are more advanced technology-based materials which respondents are adept. These kind of Technology-Based Materials are the second to the most common tools used by the students in communicating with each other due to the accessibility of internet connectivity in their community. However, it observed that cellular phones and internets adversely affect the reading levels as Igbokwe (2012) manifested that spending most of their time in the computer/internet and cellular phones and not spending time in reading and writing would result in the decline of their scholastic achievement. This study implies that the more students spend most of their time in the cyber cafes, browsing, playing games, texting through sending SMS with friends, the more they tend to become lazy in engaging in serious reading.

Table 4 Language Environment of Grade 9 Students under Printed Reading Materials

Language Environment Printed Reading Materials	f	%	Rank
Books/Textbooks	63	66%	1
Newspapers/Magazines	3	3%	3
Dictionaries/Thesaurus	29	30%	2
Pocketbooks/Novels	1	1%	4
Total	96	100%	

Table 4 shows that books are available in the school than any forms of mass media as confirmed by 63 or 66% of the respondents. Hamra and Syatriana, (2012) proves that the ability to read would enable the students to deal effectively with numerable printed materials and many other types of technical materials that they encounter in the course of learning. Therefore, the improvement of reading of the students should be the focus of teaching and learning process in increasing the human quality; otherwise, it would result in failure in learning the academic subjects.

Also, students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School asked what language preferences they tend to use in these language environmental materials available in school, home, and community. This preferred language of the respondents from the identified indicators was numbered to their corresponding equivalents which shown Tables 5 and 6.

Language Preference of Grade 9 Junior High Students

Tables 5, 6 and 7 highlight the language preference of the respondents regarding the different platforms identified in this study.

Table 5 Language Preference of Grade 9 Students in Terms of Mass Media

Mass Media	Television			Radio			Music Gadget			Over-all %	Over-all Rank
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank		
English	5	5%	3.5th	2	2%	5th	32	33%	2nd	14%	Fourth
Filipino	33	34%	2nd	26	27%	2nd	10	10%	3rd	24%	Second
Filipino-English	52	54%	1st	20	21%	3rd	41	43%	1st	39%	First
Tandaganon	1	1%	5th	43	45%	1st	5	5%	5th	17%	Third
Other Language	5	5%	3.5th	5	5%	4th	8	8%	4th	6%	Fifth
Total	96	100%		96	100%		96	100%		100%	

Table 5 shows that language preference of the students regarding mass media is the spoken language Filipino-English as confirmed by 39% of the respondents while the English language gained only 20% almost the last in mass media. The Philippines' Filipino-English spoken language commonly used as observed by Fritz (2011) that bilingual students' preferences differed across environment they spoke most at home. Robertson (2013) opined that in the

mass communication, speech designed not only for a few people to hear but an unknown mass of the population. In fact, Liu (2013) believed that the ultimate goal of language instruction is to equip learners with the ability to use the language for their communication. This result further explains that in the Philippines, Filipino-English spoken language is commonly used by students.

Table 6 Language Preference of Grade 9 Students in Terms of Technology-Based Materials

Technology-Based Materials	Computer/Internet			Cell phones			Movie/DVD			Over-all %	Over-all Rank
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank		
English	52	54%	1st	16	17%	4th	35	36%	1st	36%	First
Filipino	5	5%	3.5th	24	25%	2nd	26	27%	3rd	19%	Third
Filipino-English	30	31%	2nd	32	33%	1st	29	30%	2nd	32%	Second
Tandaganon	5	5%	3.5th	21	22%	3rd	0	0%	5th	9%	Fourth
Other Language	4	4%	5th	3	3%	5th	6	6%	4th	4%	Fifth
Total	96	100%		96	100%		96	100%		100%	

Table 6 reveals that 36% of the respondents preferred English in engaging this type of language environment while Filipino-English spoken language observed by 32% of the respondents followed by Filipino by 19% and Tandaganon by 9% while other language obtained with 4%. This result implies that the respondents are more interested in using foreign language than other languages. Indeed, the use of technology-based materials was emphasized by Robertson (2013) that this kind of manner is primarily dependent on the audience with whom they are speaking to, speakers design their style primarily for and in response to their audience. Furthermore, Igbokwe (2012) mentioned that students are rarely

interested in using the foreign language in interacting with peers for better communication.

Table 7 observes that 40% of the respondents preferred reading materials in English-Filipino especially in books, newspapers/magazines, and dictionaries/thesaurus while 27% of the respondents declared English as their language preference. This result was supported by Mai & Iwashita, (2012) that instead of traditional whole-class settings, they prefer to participate in communicative activities that enable them to use the language own language preference to express themselves, explore problems and exchange ideas with their friends to acquire knowledge.

Table 7 Language Preference of Grade 9 Students in Terms of Printed Reading Materials

Printed Reading Materials	Books			Newspapers/ Magazines			Dictionaries/ Thesaurus			Pocketbooks/ Novels			Over-all %	Over-all Rank
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank		
English	25	26%	2nd	21	22%	3rd	32	33%	2nd	25	26%	3rd	27%	Second
Filipino	22	23%	3rd	33	34%	2nd	10	10%	3rd	36	38%	1st	26%	Third
Filipino-English	43	45%	1st	37	39%	1st	41	43%	1st	32	33%	2nd	40%	First
Tandaganon	0	0%	5th	4	4%	4th	5	5%	5th	2	2%	4th	3%	Fifth
Other Language	6	6%	4th	1	1%	5th	8	8%	4th	1	1%	5th	4%	Fourth
Total	96	100%		96	100%		96	100%		96	100%		100%	

Language Proficiency Levels of Grade 9 Students

The language test employed in this study measured the level of proficiency of students since the test item had been statistically proven dependable. The test is composed of 50 items which consisted of eight parts: I. Grammar, II. Structure, III. Idiomatic Expressions, IV. Vocabulary, V. Verbal Analogy, VII. Logical Organization, VII. Identification of Errors, and VIII. Reading Comprehension. There were two sections of Grade 9 students tapped comprising 96 respondents. The average mean per area of language proficiency indicated in Table 8.

Table 8 English Proficiency Levels in Eight Language Areas

Language Areas	% Score	Level of Proficiency
Grammar	39%	Developing
Sentence Structure	29%	Developing
Idioms	31%	Developing
Vocabulary	27%	Developing
Verbal Analogy	28%	Developing
Logical Organization	37%	Developing
Identification of Errors	24%	Beginning
Reading Comprehension	36%	Developing
Over-all Percentage Score	31%	Developing

Table 8 elucidates that majority of the respondents are on Developing stage particularly in the language areas in Grammar, Sentence Structure, Idioms, Vocabulary, Verbal Analogy, Logical Organization, Reading Comprehension with the overall percentage score of 31%. According to Eldoumi (2012) that these language areas are central to the teaching and learning

of a language. On the other hand, 24% of the respondents are still on "Beginning" stage in the area of Identification of Errors. This result proves that identification of errors is one of the challenging aspects of language to teach well since it is a thought of fixed word forms and rules of usage. This result in line with what (NCLRC) ascertained that on strategic competence where the students would know how to repair communication. Everhard, Cooper, and Bock (2005) also stressed the importance of sentence sense in comprehension.

Significant Relationship between Language Preference and the English Proficiency

The study determined if the students' language preference and English language proficiency have a significant relationship. Table 9 deduces that majority of the students' English Language Areas are predominantly "not significant" in relation to language preference in Grammar (p- 0.321), Sentence Structure (p-0.721), Vocabulary (p-0.243), Verbal Analogy (p-0.736), Logical Organization (p-0.497), Identification of Errors (p-0.344), and Reading Comprehension (p-0.245). This study implies that the not significant relationship between variables meant that regarding grammar and other components inclined to syntax; there is an underlying implication that the language preferred by the respondents with that of the English language has a difference because of the varied meanings of languages.

On the other hand, it is evident from the results that the students' English language area on Idioms ($r=0.211$) is significantly related to the language preference of the respondents at the p-value of 0.039.

This result led us to reject the hypothesis to a significant relationship. This underscores that the meaning is relative. Hence, respondents do not meet challenges regarding meaning making. Thus, this indicates that the students with poor English proficiency do not perform well in the class. On the same ground, the study of Alngog (2013) revealed

that a significant relationship between the proficiency in the English language in expressing their ideas could hardly communicate various thoughts because of lack of mastery of the English language. The majority is bereft of the lack of language skills.

Table 9 further explicates the significant relationship between language preference and the English proficiency of the respondents.

Table 9 Significant Relationship between Language Preference and Language Area

Language Areas	Computed r	p-value	Conclusion
Language Preference in relation to Grammar	0.102	0.321	Not Significant
Language Preference in relation to Sentence Structure	0.037	0.721	Not Significant
Language Preference in relation to Idioms	0.211	0.039	Significant
Language Preference in relation to Vocabulary	0.120	0.243	Not Significant
Language Preference in relation to Verbal Analogy	0.035	0.736	Not Significant
Language Preference in relation to Logical Organization	0.070	0.497	Not Significant
Language Preference in relation to Identification of Errors	0.098	0.344	Not Significant
Language Preference in relation to Reading Comprehension	0.120	0.245	Not Significant

5. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter delineates the summary of findings, states the conclusions and identifies some recommendations.

Summary of Findings

By the preceding study the following findings were drawn:

On the Exposure of the Grade 9 Students

Among the three groups of language environment under mass media, television is the most available in their school, community, and home other than any types of media where the respondents exposed. The use of cellular phones is the preferred technology-based materials that the respondents are hooked up to, second with the utilizations of computer/internet. Books are readily available in the school than any forms of mass media under printed reading materials.

As to the language preference regarding mass media, Filipino-English spoken language is commonly used with 39% of the respondents while the English language gained only 20% almost the last preferred in mass media. The students' preferred language is English in understanding the use of technology-based materials such as computer, the internet (sending emails, researching, chatting, social networking,

facebook, twitter, Instagram); sending text messages and watching DVD/movies. The preferred language regarding printed reading materials is Filipino-English spoken language especially in reading books, newspapers/magazines, and dictionaries/thesaurus.

On the other hand, the language proficiency levels of Grade 9 students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School are: Grammar - 39% (Developing), Structure - 29% (Developing), Idiomatic Expressions - 31% (Developing), Vocabulary - 27% (Developing), Verbal Analogy - 28% (Developing), Logical Organization - 37% (Developing), Identification of Errors - 24% (Developing), and Reading Comprehension - 36% (Developing). The overall percentage score is "developing" with 31%.

As to the Significant Relationship between Language Preference and the English Proficiency, the correlation coefficient between the Language Preference and the English Proficiency of the p-value is less than .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis rejected. Thus, there is a significant relationship of the two variables. As far as Language Preference on Idioms of the computed 0.211 and p-value of 0.039 obtained to rejecting the hypothesis. Thus, it establish the significant relationship and conclusion of the study.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the study concludes that the Grade 9 Students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School manifest a decline in their English proficiency due to spending more time in television than reading books in their school, home, and community. In effect, students complain that they could hardly understand a language that is not native to them even they try all the means to learn it. To them, even how competent their teachers are in the language, still they could hardly attain proficiency.

Further, the study concludes that the use of cellphones and the utilizations of computer, the internet like sending emails, chatting on Facebook, twitter, Instagram, Edmodo, etc would imply negative implications for the students to become proficient in English especially that on Facebook. For example, these group of students are using their own mother tongue and does not help to improve their becoming proficient in English. Also, more students spend most of their time in the cyber cafes, browsing, playing games, texting through sending SMS with friends which result in the decline in engaging to reading for both academic and entertainment purposes.

Likewise, the study concludes that due to their more exposure in mass media/social media like facebook, these students preferred to speak a combination of Filipino and English. This investigation is evident on the result of the study that English fall under on the last language. The students observed to be unable to express their thoughts in fluent English; thus, to emphasize what they want to articulate, they tend to code switch in Filipino. Because of this, their language fell under the developing level.

Furthermore, the study concludes that a significant relationship between the proficiency in the English language in expressing their ideas could hardly communicate various thoughts because of the difficulties in interpretations of information, deducing meaning and summarizing ideas. All these boil down to the problem on applying idioms, leading the students not to understand what they are reading. They are not developing proficiency in the language. They have difficulty in expressing their ideas in spoken and written form.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions, several recommendations offered to English teachers and

other academic subject teachers, students, school administrators, curriculum designers and developers, and other research enthusiasts.

The English teachers of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School may continuously update themselves with new approaches, methods, strategies and techniques in teaching the English subject. This recommendation can be done by attending seminars, trainings, and workshops related to language and literature teaching. Through this, they can bring out innovations like integrating Computer Aided Instructional Materials and other forms of social media such as Youtube, Quipper, Edmodo, Twitter, Skype, interactive powerpoint, etc. In their teaching and that the proficiency of the students in the English language will increased.

The other Academic teachers handling subjects like Science and Mathematics of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School are encouraged to support the English Program of the school by promoting the use of English language in their classes. Also, they can serve as the model to their students in the use of the language and incorporate real life tasks that require the students to apply the English language while learning the concepts in Science and Mathematics.

The Grade 9 students of Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School are suggested to expose them in computer-aided instructional materials using ICT to realize the importance of English language in learning English, Science and Mathematics concepts. They need to understand the English language as a system and of the role of its components so as to understand its demands on academic tasks and eventually gain skills to address the role of academic language in their learning.

The school principal is recommended to have concrete plans to develop and monitor their students' English language proficiency throughout their stay in the institution by allocating resources that contribute to the students' English language proficiency program.

Lastly, the curriculum designers and other research enthusiasts are suggested to revisit the existing curriculum programs especially in English by taking into consideration the result of the study.

PROPOSED ENHANCEMENT TRAINING PROGRAM FOR TEACHERS IN ENGLISH PROFICIENCY

Rationale

The English language proficiency of the Grade 9 students in Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School, District of Cagwait was investigated through their levels of proficiency based on the Mean Percentage Score. The study indicates that majority of the students fall under developing level.

This means that there is a dire need to examine the teaching practices of teachers providing instruction in English proficiency since students rely on language proficiency to succeed academically. Nevertheless, the positive relationship observed from the study means that the increase of one variable leads to an increase in the other. In other words, the more proficient in English a student is, the better he/she is in academics.

This implies that if the teachers will put serious efforts to improve language proficiency in English better performance would be expected from the students. On the other hand, a weak positive relationship revealed from the study shows that students do not learn because of their weaknesses in language proficiency. This is to say, the government should devote itself seriously to improve proficiency in English, otherwise students will not be learning effectively. It is therefore, a necessary to design appropriate language intervention program for teachers that would cater adequately on the language skills of the students which will be instituted this summer.

I. Program Objectives

The primary goal of this program is to reinforce the levels of English language proficiency of the teachers with various techniques in order to increase the academic performance of the students in English.

During the implementation phase, the objectives are as follows:

1. Enrich the language of instruction of the English teachers in Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School using various strategies in teaching;
2. Intensify on the use of strategic instructional materials during classes;
3. Conduct festival of talents in the form of literary arts such as speech choir, oration, extemporaneous, jazz chants, spelling bee,

chamber theatre, essay writing, and other related co-curricular activities;

4. Institutionalize INSET program for English teachers in the cluster during semester break and summer vacations;
5. Prepare a supervisory program that will include monitoring, evaluation and follow-up of content knowledge and skills acquired by English teachers during trainings/seminars to ensure that the acquired skills and knowledge are put into good use in improving their teaching efficiency. Follow up in the classroom should also be done.

II. Project Description

The Project title of the English language intervention program for teachers is called **Turning Around Low Performance in English, or Project TURN**. It is a program that aims to improve the performance of students in Jose Sanvictores Sr. National School. The program also aims to attain a 5% increase MPS of the schools every year starting SY 20017-2018. The current emphasis of Project TURN is on improving the English proficiency of teachers through additional training and material support which is cited upon as one of the key factors for the improvement of NAT scores.

➤ Contents

The implementation of the Project TURN is composed of six parts: Assessment, Intervention Package for Teachers, Intervention Package for Students, Intervention Package for Schools, Support Program and Policy Enhancement and Implementation.

➤ Assessment

Under Project TURN, both teachers and students are required to undergo assessment measures to accurately pinpoint problem areas in English. All teachers who teach subjects that are taught in English are required to take the Teachers' English Proficiency Test, and students from grade 9 are required to take the English test. The outcome of the assessment will be the basis in identifying specific language learning activities.

➤ Intervention Package for Teachers

After the assessment, teachers shall be trained in the areas of oral and written communication, authentic assessment in communication, communicative language teaching, and teaching beginning, developmental and remedial reading. Materials, both

print and non-print, shall also be provided for teachers. The following are some of the language skills, contents, strategies, and approaches and activities to support the development of the four English language skills:

- **Remedial measures for speaking skills**

Any learner who sets himself in a learning atmosphere like schools will get enough opportunity to come across new words and its meaning appropriated to the situation. The moment he leaves the atmosphere there won't be enough drills and works which gets him to come across new words. In such a scenario the language users must find an alternate source to get new words and its meaning. Two activities will certainly create a room to build their vocabulary (i) Reading, (ii) Listening to audios. These two activities will certainly give a measure to build one's vocabulary, since the user will come across lots of new words from which the reader can understand the meanings and the usage of new words.

Reading and Listening to audios alone will not get one to know more, whenever one comes across new words he has to refer either to a dictionary or online source to find its meaning and usage. Later, he has to do some homework by talking to himself or in front of a mirror by using those words. He has to keep doing this on a regular basis until he gets perfect with those words with consistency in their normal usage. More than in reading the user can benefit from listening mode to build his vocabulary, though it clears the problem of pronunciation too. When a word is pronounced correctly, it definitely sounds beautiful, then almost 20% of proficiency acquires from this act. Apart from vocabulary building the users get additional benefits of these two activities. It enhances knowledge and resource and keeps them updated if they are in terms of current affairs. In addition to reading and listening users can use many activities for vocabulary building like playing puzzles and word games like scrabbles and fables etc.

Listening to lots of audios will certainly help one to identify and differentiate the accent, and practicing the basis of vowels and consonants will make one to understand the relationship of words and sounds. These will certainly enhance one's voice & accent and they apply using it in their personal life, one's voice along with accent will get emulate.

There are only three things to mind when it comes to Voice & Accent (i) Pronunciation, (ii) Intonation, (iii) Rate of speech. If a person learns to manage him or herself in all the three, then it would be an easy task to modulate the barriers. In pronunciation, identification of the syllable in the words is more important, once it is done the rest depends on using the right vowel and consonant sound. To resolve these measures it is mandated to learn the forty four sounds of English language and start applying it practically.

In Intonation, one has to identify the scenario of usage, a same sentence will be considered in different meaning which depends on what is emphasized. There are three elements which will certainly acquire one to improve better on their intonation (i) Loudness, (ii) Stretch, and (ii) Pitch. One has to consistently practice in these areas to acquire perfection in Intonation.

The amount of words used in speech is known as rate of speech. One must understand the fast speech will not make much sense to the listeners, and neither the slow one. This problem can be rectified only in terms of consciousness. The user needs to maintain a caution while speaking to others in the beginning, by self-instructing themselves to maintain a good rate of speech which is assumed to be 30 – 40 words per minute in a speech.

- **Remedial measures for Reading skills**

The procedure of going through a text or a passage in order to get the subject inside one's mind is known as reading. This habitual certainly makes a person knowledgeable and resourceful. The protocol of reading is been explained from the basis studies, one must know the letters, spellings, meaning of the words and the knowledge of content understanding. Not everyone is been gifted with this skill, most of them find it difficult in doing this. Many reasons are traced, but the common issues which are found in most of the cases are described as reading barriers.

It is certain that if a person needs to be educated in any domain, can't skip this skill, but still many of them are not in the marks when it comes to reading. The ultimate reason is lack of Interest. It is nature that the entire humanity prefers to listen to understand things, rather than reading. To understand things better, reading is the best option. No one can create self-interest towards anything, but the suggestion opted as if one is determined to know more and to be resourceful, he has to spend time in reading books in

any at least minimum of 30 minutes a day. Once they acquired reading habit with this limits, then slowly they need to step forward by increasing the spending hours, in fortnight by default reading will become as a habit and interest towards reading will be developed by default.

Another barrier identified for reading is the appliance of skimming and scanning. The current generation prefers to apply this term while reading anything nowadays, since the load of work is heavy, consisted too much of workload which needs to be covered in short time, nevertheless it becomes common among students. This habitual will also create a boredom towards reading on later stages. In order to avoid this, one has to avoid applying the terminology of skimming and scanning while reading at least in the scenario where it can be avoided. Practicing these terms will certainly emulate one in the process of reading.

- **Remedial measures for writing skills**

The art of “writing makes a perfect man” says Francis Bacon. Writing is not a definite measure for everyone; it is quite different with the rest of the skills. The above three skills Listening, Speaking, and Reading, are found common among everyone. If one enhances himself in those skills, it really makes him to stand on better ground. But writing skill is unique and exempted from the above skills. Writing is used for conveyance of message and documentation. The history of this world, science, and even religion is conveyed through the process of writing.

Many people tend to write but wouldn't succeed due to writing barriers, even in this skill, there are some barriers identified for writing which can be resolved through practical training. The more one writes the better gets perfect. Every student can see difference in his writings from age to age and standard to standard, completely depends upon one's level of maturity and level of understanding. Age factor plays a vital role in gaining experience, once it accumulates in a person; he or she needs to start practicing in communicating it through writing. In the beginning everyone will find it tough to explore his ideas exact in the manner he feels or thinks, when day goes on the more he writes slowly and steadily the more will acquire them. Writing and reading are co-related. When one acquires mastery and does a lot of reading by default he turns into a good writing. The struck up and struggle will not occur to set his point while writing.

Another barrier for writing is continuous overflow of emotions. This problem occurs in many professional writers; they get lot of point than they write. This problem comes to people who write while thinking themselves. The only solutions for this problem is to make a practice of thinking first and then write about it. Even in this formula there is a problem. Most of them wouldn't recollect and remember all the points they thought. To overcome this problem one must practice the habit of note making and hint making through shorthand or in any of his favorite style which could be accessible for him to recover the entire content of creation.

- **Remedial Measures for Listening skills**

Despite it is the most proficient skill that the respondents were rated, it is of paramount importance to initiate some measures that would enhance more the ability of the students to listen critically since this skill is intertwined with the other three macro skills in the language areas of concern. In addition, the capacity of human visualization is intended into many aspects like hallucination, delusion, fantasy, imagination, daydreaming, like more. These elements can be considered as skills or else a curse depends upon the level of the appliance. Nowadays it's been a common problem for most of them, diverse from students to scholars in different domain. Some of them take advantage of it and use it for their personal and career growth, but most in cases it lies in defeat. Once a person got into these, it will surpass him to different levels and it is a tough task to get out of it. It takes special training and motivation to re frame them.

There are two types of daydreaming (i) sleep mode means a person will only dream or think something out of the box only when their eyes are closed. (ii) active mode means a person will still dream, or think something out of the box even by keeping their eyes open, it occurs normal to every human being, but to some people it gets worst in which they miss lot importance that happens in and around them. This is the biggest barrier of listening skill. It's been said a child learns to speak by listening to his surroundings and it's quite natural to understand which opts even for second language learners.

One can get perfection in a language only he or she gets lots of good listening. The art of meditation will certainly help one to overcome this barrier. One must have a good control over their mind, body, and soul

which can be acquired through meditation. Thus, it prevents one to daydream and to get focused onto the subject and helps their listening ability. Inaudibility is another barrier which prevents listening skill, there are several reasons for these acts, (i) it could be physical disabilities or mental disabilities, (ii) Noise and voice pollution.

One has to identify with what complications they suffer from, after the identification if it is due to physical or mental discomfort they have to approach a physician for suggestions which may recover for those cases, if it is noise or voice pollution they've to make necessary environmental conditions which can resolve the pollution.

Deeply Interpreting a concept is another problem that lies in listening skill, which is not good in most of the cases, many of the people got struck with the problem, while one interpret on a said concept they miss the rest of words which may be equally important. To overcome this barrier one must practice qualities like note taking, hints making, and gadget recordings these will certainly help to overcome this barrier.

➤ **Intervention Package for Students**

The intervention package for students primarily focuses more on the provision of supplementary reading materials and other auxiliary programs such as medical/dental or feeding assistance. As stated earlier, Project TURN focuses more on training teachers to be able to teach better in order to improve the performance of the students. In return, students are expected to develop English language proficiency by acquiring knowledge in the specific English proficiency skills.

➤ **Intervention Package for Schools**

The intervention package for schools concentrates more on the development and implementation of information and communication technology-based reading models to be used by students and teachers. This is accompanied by the provision of the necessary materials and training to facilitate the ICT based models, plus the construction of a speech laboratory to be set up in each high school. Traditional methods to help students learn English, such as books, are also included as the package also provides for an initial library collection for every school.

➤ **Support Program**

Co-curricular activities are also integrated in Project TURN, such as conducting Speech Arts Competitions and Summer Reading Camps during school breaks. Activities for teachers, such as the organization of a "Search for the Best Reading Teacher and Best School in Reading," will also be held to encourage the active participation of teachers in the program. The private sector is also tapped to support the program by helping out in the organization of the reading camps, the acquisition of materials and the updating of library collections.

➤ **Policy Enhancement and Implementation**

Policies will be also set in place by the DepEd to institutionalize the program, such as a one English textbook-one student ratio as well as the adoption of the Every Child A Reader Program's reading models - beginning, developmental and remedial reading - plus its best practices. The DepEd also aims to institutionalize the provision of a library or reading center for every school.

III. Operating Details

- A. Participants: The participants to this intervention program are the English teachers in the secondary schools of Cagwait and school administrators.
- B. Resource Persons: The speakers are composed of pool of experts in English. These are the Master Teachers in English of Cagwait, Division Education Program Supervisor in English, and Program Specialists in English.
- C. Training Duration: The training program shall start in Summer of 2017 and the full implementation of the program shall begin in the opening of classes in June 2017 and be institutionalized in all the secondary schools of Cagwait.

IV. Budgetary Requirements

A. Honoraria for the speakers(4XP500)	-P2,000.00
B. Training Supplies	-2,000.00
C. Supplies for the intervention materials	-10,000.00
D. Sound System @ 500.00 for 3 days	-1,500.00
E. Food Accommodations (Meals & Snacks @ 200)	- 5,000.00
	(25 participants X 200.00 X 3days)
	TOTAL: P30, 500.00

In order to defray the expenses covered during the 3-day in-service training, the expenses shall be sourced from the following:

- A. Teachers' Registration Fee chargeable against school MOOE (16 teachers and administrators as participants X P500.00) -P10, 500.00
- B. Local School Board through Special Education Funds - 20,000.00
- Proposed Total Budget: P30, 500.00

V. Project Sustainability Plan

In order to sustain the implementation of the Project TURN Intervention Program, the following activities are herein laid and proposed:

1. Conduct yearly monitoring and evaluation mechanisms align to the DepEd's VMGO by discussing with target group the accomplishment vs-a-vis performance targets;
2. Focus on school effectiveness program implementation policies in relation to curriculum development and instructional supervision as provided in the annual plan;
3. Increase classroom monitoring and observation of school head and Division Monitoring Team;
4. Create a convention of English teachers in the four high schools of Cagwait through benchmarking and sharing of best practices and exchange ideas based on the experience and find out applicable solutions to the problems encountered;
5. Improve availability of instructional and learning support materials;
6. Implement effective school management and administration through intensifying instructional supervision, Parents' Participation, and Resource mobilization efforts.

Table 10 Proposed Enhancement Training Program for Teachers in English Proficiency

TIME	Day 1	Day2	Day 3
7:30-8:00	Registration	Unfreezing Activities	Unfreezing Activities
8:00-9:00	Opening Program	Approaches and Strategies in Teaching Writing	Presentation of Computer Aided Instructional Materials in Strategies
9:00-10:00	Nature and Approaches in Learning English Language		
10:00-10:15	SNACKS		
10:15-12:00	Approaches and Strategies in Teaching Speaking	Approaches and Strategies in Teaching Listening	English Proficiency Assessment Tools
12:00-1:00	LUNCHBREAK		
1:00-2:00	Approaches and Strategies in Teaching Reading	Use of Multi-Media in Instruction	Return Teaching Demo and Critiquing
2:00-3:00			
3:00-4:00	Reading Comprehension Strategies	Development of Computer Aided Instructional Materials	Closing Program
4:00-5:00			

VI. The English Language Proficiency Matrices

The English language proficiency standards reflect the academic dimensions of acquiring a second language that are expected to yield better academic performance. The language domains reflect the modality of the communication that is further delineated by the language proficiency levels and their model performance indicators.

The five **language proficiency levels** outline the progression of language development implied in the acquisition of English as an additional language, from 1. Entering the process, to 5. Bridging to the attainment of state academic content standards. The language proficiency levels delineate expected performance and describe what English language learners can do within each domain of the standards. The language proficiency levels serve as stepping stones along the pathway to academic success where English language learners cross

the bridge from English language proficiency to meet academic content standards of the Department of Education. With these teaching training matrices, it has given the impetus to embark on the journey of redefining English language proficiency standards, tied to their academic content standards as the basis for the development of English language proficiency measures

Figure3. The Levels of English Language Proficiency and Academic Achievement for English Language Learners

Table11. Performance Definitions for the English Language Proficiency Standards

At the given level of English language proficiency, English language learners will process, understand, produce, or use:	
Level 5- Bridging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the technical language of the content areas; • a variety of sentence lengths of varying linguistic complexity in extended oral or written discourse, including stories, essays, or reports; ➤ oral or written language approaching comparability to that of English proficient peers when presented with grade level material
Level 4- Expanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • specific and some technical language of the content areas; • a variety of sentence lengths of varying linguistic complexity in oral discourse or multiple, related paragraphs; ➤ oral or written language with minimal phonological, syntactic, or semantic errors that do not impede the overall meaning of the communication when presented with oral or written connected discourse with occasional visual and graphic support
Level 3- Developing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • general and some specific language of the content areas; • expanded sentences in oral interaction or written paragraphs; ➤ oral or written language with phonological, syntactic, or semantic errors that may impede the communication but retain much of its meaning when presented with oral or written, narrative or expository descriptions with occasional visual and graphic support
Level 2- Beginning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • general language related to the content areas; • phrases or short sentences; ➤ oral or written language with phonological, syntactic, or semantic errors that often impede the meaning of the communication when presented with one to multiple-step commands, directions, questions, or a series of statements with visual and graphic support
Level 1- Entering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pictorial or graphic representation of the language of the content areas; • words, phrases, or chunks of language when presented with one-step commands, directions, WH-questions, or statements with visual and graphic support

REFERENCES CITED

1. Abebe, T. T., & Davidson, L. M. (2012). "Assessing the Role of Visual Teaching Materials in Teaching English Vocabulary". *Language in India*, 12(3), 524.
2. Aduwa-Ogiegbaen, S. E., & Iyamu, E. O. S. (2006). "Factors Affecting Quality of English Language Teaching English Language Teaching" Vol. 7, No. 8; 2014 104 Learning in secondary schools in Nigeria. *College Student Journal*, pp40, 495. www.ccsenet.org/elt.
3. Alngog, Ponciano G. (2013). "English Language Proficiency Levels of Grade 7 Students of JPENHS: Basis for a Language Enhancement Program". Unpublished Thesis. Graduate School, Surigao del Sur State University, Tandag City.
4. Arpilleda, Charito Luluh L. (2013). "Instructional Management of English Teaching and Its Effect on the Proficiency of the Language Among Fourth Year Students of Leyte State University Laboratory High School." Thesis. Leyte State University.
5. Breen, M., & Candlin, C. N. (2010). "The Essentials of a Communicative Curriculum in Language Teaching". *Applied Linguistics*, 1(2), 89-112. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/applin/I.2.89>.
6. Brown, H. D., (2007a). "Principles of language learning and teaching", (5th Ed.). White Plains, NY: Pearson Longman.
7. Brown, H. D., (2007b). "Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy" (3rd Ed.). USA: San Francisco State University.
8. Cook, V., (2001). "Second Language Learning and Language Teaching", (3rd Ed.). London: Arnold.
9. Creswell, J. W., (2009). "Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches", (3rd Ed.). Thousand Oaks, Calif.: Sage Publications.
10. Dang, H. V., (2006). "Learner-Centeredness and EFL Instruction in Vietnam: A Case Study". *International Education Journal*, 7(4), 598-610.
11. Everhard, Kathleen M., J. Cooper and Kathryn Bock. (2005). "Making Syntax of Sense: Number Agreement in Sentence Production." *Psychological Review*. Vol. 112, No. 3. American Psychological Association. Web 10 January 2016. <http://www.ling.umd.edu>
12. Gao, L., (2012). "Digital Technologies and English Instruction in China's Higher Education System: Teacher Development". <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13664530.2012.667967>.
13. Harman, G. S., Hayden, M., & Pham, T. N., (2010). "Reforming Higher Education in Vietnam: Challenges and priorities". Dordrecht: Springer.
14. Igbokwe, J.C., Nnenna Obidike and E.C. Ezeji., (2012). "Influence of Electronic Media on Reading Ability of School Children" Thesis. University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria.
15. Jacobs, G. M., Hall, S., & J. C. Richards, & A. W. Renandya (Eds.), (2002). "Implementing Cooperative Learning Methodology in language teaching: An Anthology of Current Practice", (pp. 52-53). New York: Cambridge University Press.
16. Le, V. C., (2009). "Language and Vietnamese pedagogical contexts". Paper Presented at the Fourth International Conference on Language and Development, Hanoi.
17. Littlewood, W., (2011). "Communicative Language Teaching: An Introduction". Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
18. Liu, L., (2003). "A New Perspective on the Goals of TEFL in China". *The internet TESL Journal*, IX (11).
19. Liu, M., & Zhang, L., (2007). "Student Perceptions Of Native And Non-Native English Teachers' Attitudes, Teaching Skills Assessment and Performance". *Asian EFL Journal*, 9(4), 157-166.
20. Lochana, M., & Deb, G., (2006). "Task-Based Teaching: Learning English without Tears". *Asian EFL Journal*, 8(3), 140-164.
21. Mai, N. K., & Iwashita, N., (2012). "A Comparison of Learners' and Teachers' Attitudes Toward Communicative Language Teaching at Two Universities in Vietnam". *University of Sydney Papers in TESOL*, 7, 25-49.
22. Mathew, N. G., & Alidmat, A. O. H., (2013). "A study on the Usefulness of Audio-Visual Aids in EFL Classrooms: Implications for Effective Instruction". *International Journal of Higher Education*, 2. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v2n2p86>.
23. Mondal, N. K., (2011). "Evaluation of English Language Teaching Methods Used in Higher

- Secondary Education in Bangladesh*” (Report). Language in India, 11(12), 181.
24. Nguyen, T. H. A., (2012). “*Cultural effects on learning and teaching English in Vietnam*”. The Language Teacher, 26.
25. Nhan, N. T., & Lai, H. T., (2012). “*The Enhancement of Learner Autonomy and the Growth of English Language Proficiency*” (Report). Language in India, 12(4), 427.
26. Paropcar, Anusha and Ramcharan. , (2010). “*Language Proficiency and Academic Performance: A Case Study for Secondary School.*” Thesis. University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban.
27. Pham, T. H. T., (2006). “*The Development of the Higher Education Sector of Vietnam within the Globalization Discourse: Using Futures Methodologies*”. *Journal of Futures Studies*, 11(2), 35-60.
28. Richards, J. C., (2001). “*Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching*” (2nd Ed.). Cambridge, U.K.
29. Tin Tan, D., (2010). “*Learner Autonomy in EFL Studies in Vietnam: A Discussion from Sociocultural Perspective*”. *English Language Teaching*, 3(2).
30. Tomlinson, B., & Dat, B., (2014). “*The Contributions of Vietnamese Learners of English to ELT Methodology*”. www.ccsenet.org/elt English Language Teaching Vol. 7, No. 8; 105 Language Teaching Research, 8(2), 199-222. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1191/1362168804lr140oa.2004>.
31. VO, L. T., & Nguyen, H. T. M., (2010). “*Critical Friends Group for EFL Teacher Professional Development*”. *ELT Journal*, 64(2), 205-211 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccp025>.
32. Yilmaz, C., “*Teachers’ Perceptions of Self-Efficacy, English Proficiency, and Instructional Strategies*” (Report). *Social Behavior and Personality: An International Journal*, 39(1), 91. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2224/sbp.2011.39.1.91>. 2011;

